

AutoML: A Tertiary Study of Phases, Methods, Tools, and Frameworks

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Abstract. Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) plays a pivotal role in making machine learning more accessible by automating key steps in the model development process. Over the past decade, an increasing number of literature reviews (LRs) have examined specific components of AutoML, including data preparation, feature engineering, model generation, neural architecture search, hyperparameter optimization, and evaluation. However, a unified synthesis that consolidates findings across these reviews is missing. This paper presents a tertiary review of 32 LRs to provide a comprehensive and up-to-date overview of the AutoML landscape. We systematically analyze the core AutoML phases, categorize AutoML methods used across different stages of the machine learning (ML) pipeline, and compile a set of AutoML frameworks and tools. The synthesis offers a panoramic view of the techniques and tools supporting automation across ML phases. Our findings aim to serve as a reference for researchers and practitioners seeking to understand the current state of AutoML, the extent of automation achieved across pipeline stages, and the tools and platforms that support these capabilities.

Keywords: Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) · Tertiary Study · Literature Review (LR) · AutoML Tools and Frameworks · Automation in Machine Learning (ML).

A Appendix: AutoML Methods and Tools

This supplementary appendix provides detailed tables referenced in the main text. It includes: (A.1) AutoML techniques and tools used for data preparation; (A.2) feature engineering methods and frameworks; (A.3) optimization strategies applied across different pipeline phases; (A.4) an overview of pipeline optimization frameworks; and (A.5) evaluation methods employed in AutoML systems. These resources aim to enhance transparency, replicability, and offer a consolidated view of operational techniques and tools across the AutoML lifecycle.

A.1 AutoML Techniques and Tools for Data Preparation

Table 1 summarizes key techniques and tools commonly used for automating data preparation in AutoML systems.

Table 1: AutoML Techniques and Tools for Data Preparation

Subtask	Technique	Tool/Framework	Reference
Data Cleaning	Error detection and repairing	BoostClean, AlphaClean, Katara	[P21]
Data Cleaning	Missing value imputation	Auto-sklearn, H2O AutoML	[P21]
Data Cleaning	Outlier/infinity removal	Auto-sklearn	[P21]
Data Cleaning	Feature scaling (e.g., normalization, standardization)	Auto-sklearn, TransmogriAI	[P21,P15]
Data Cleaning	Integrity constraints and logic rules	Katara	[P21]
Data Cleaning	Greedy search-based cleaning pipeline	BoostClean, AlphaClean	[P21]
Data Cleaning	Pipeline-aware metafeature validation	Auto-sklearn, DataRobot	[P21]
Data Curation	ML-based dataset linking and cleaning	DataRobot, AlphaClean	[P11,P15]
Data Curation	Interactive/Active data cleaning	—	[P11]
Visualization	Visual-guided cleaning and testing	—	[P11]
Labeling	HITL, self-/co-training, co-learning	—	[P10,P15]
Encoding	Label encoding, one-hot, hashing	Auto-sklearn, TransmogriAI	[P15,P18]
Augmentation	Affine, elastic, mixup, back-translation	AutoAugment, Albumentations, MixText	[P15,P10,P1]

A.2 AutoML Techniques and Tools for Feature Engineering

Table 2 presents key techniques and tools employed in AutoML systems for automating feature engineering tasks.

Table 2: AutoML Techniques and Tools for Feature Engineering

Subtask	Technique	Tool/Framework	Reference
Feature Selection	Filter, wrapper, embedded models; stability selection	Auto-sklearn, H2O, TPOT, AutoGluon	[P10,P21,P15]
Feature Selection	Meta-feature ranking, search-based subset selection	ExploreKit	[P18]
Feature Selection	Regression-based filtering	AutoLearn	[P16,P4]
Feature Construction	Arithmetic/logical transformations; transformation trees/graphs	OneBM, Cognito	[P18]
Feature Construction	Deep Feature Synthesis for relational data	Featuretools	[P18]
Feature Construction	Expand-reduce transformation pipelines	DSM	[P18]
Feature Construction	No intermediate evaluation heuristic	OBM	[P18]
Feature Extraction	Dimensionality reduction (PCA, LDA, Autoencoders)	AutoFE, Auto-sklearn	[P10,P15]
Feature Extraction	Domain-specific extraction (TF-IDF, SIFT, etc.)	AutoFE (generic), AutoGluon	[P15]
Cross-phase	Meta-learning for transformation selection	LFE	[P18,P13]
Cross-phase	Reinforcement/genetic programming for adaptive features	AutoFE, TPOT	[P5,P18,P15]

A.3 Optimization Methods in AutoML

Table 3 outlines common optimization methods used across different phases of AutoML pipelines.

Table 3: Optimization Methods in AutoML

Category	Method	Description	AutoML Phases Supported
Black-box Optimization	Grid Search	Exhaustive evaluation of all parameter combinations [P8,P2].	HPO, CASH
Black-box Optimization	Random Search	Randomly samples configuration space, often more effective than grid in high dimensions [P7,P17,P12,P21].	HPO, CASH
Black-box Optimization	SMBO	Uses surrogate models (e.g., Gaussian Processes) to explore the performance landscape [P10].	HPO, CASH
Black-box Optimization	Bayesian Optimization	Builds a probabilistic surrogate to guide search via acquisition functions [P21,P8,P14].	HPO, CASH, NAS
Black-box Optimization	TPE	Non-parametric variant of BO modeling conditional densities for hierarchical spaces [P8,P21].	HPO, CASH
Black-box Optimization	Simulated Annealing / GA	Nature-inspired heuristics navigating rugged spaces via probabilistic transitions [P8,P14].	HPO, CASH
Black-box Optimization	Gradient-based Methods	Used in differentiable settings like DARTS for neural architecture tuning [P21].	NAS
Multi-fidelity Optimization	Successive Halving	Iteratively prunes configurations using increasing resource budgets [P3,P8].	HPO
Multi-fidelity Optimization	Hyperband	Extends SH with adaptive budget allocation [P3,P8].	HPO, CASH
Multi-fidelity Optimization	Freeze-Thaw BO	Pauses/resumes configurations based on intermediate performance [P3].	HPO
Multi-fidelity Optimization	Learning Curve Extrapolation	Predicts final performance from partial training curves [P3,P8].	HPO, NAS
Racing	iRace, ROAR	Applies statistical tests (e.g., t-test) to terminate weak configurations early [P3].	HPO
Racing	LCCV	Uses convex learning curves for early cross-validation decisions [P3].	HPO
Evolutionary Algorithms	GA, EA, RE, MSAE	Population-based search using mutation, crossover, and elitism [P19,P7].	CASH, NAS, Pipeline Opt.
Grammar-based Optimization	GGP	Constructs syntactically valid pipelines using context-free grammar [P19,P7].	Pipeline Opt., CASH
Grammar-based Optimization	HTN Planning	Decomposes tasks into sub-goals using symbolic planning [P19,P7].	Pipeline Opt.
Reinforcement Learning	RL-based Controllers	Uses reward-based neural controllers to explore search space [P7,P17,P12].	NAS, CASH
Adaptive Methods	PBT, Self-tuning Nets	Iteratively updates configurations based on performance trends [P20].	NAS, HPO
Fidelity-aware Methods	Proxy Evaluations	Uses approximations like subsampling or early stopping to reduce cost [P20].	HPO, NAS

A.4 Overview of AutoML Pipeline Optimization Frameworks

Table 4 provides an overview of key frameworks designed for pipeline optimization.

Table 4: Overview of AutoML Pipeline Optimization Frameworks

Framework	Description	Reference(s)
Auto-WEKA	Formulates the CASH problem; uses Bayesian optimization (SMAC). Auto-WEKA 2.0 adds regression and expanded metrics.	[P20,P18,P9]
Auto-sklearn	Enhances Auto-WEKA with meta-learning and ensemble construction. v2.0 adds policy-based budgeting.	[P18,P16,P20]
TPOT	Applies genetic programming to evolve pipelines using scikit-learn components.	[P18,P16]
ATM / AutoFrankensteining	Use BO and bandits for distributed AutoML and ensemble support.	[P18]
ML-Plan / AlphaD3M	ML-Plan uses hierarchical task networks; AlphaD3M applies reinforcement learning with MCTS.	[P18]
TuPAQ	Treats CASH as a query optimization problem with bandit search.	[P18]
H2O AutoML	Uses random search and stacked ensembles for robust pipelines.	[P20]
Autostacker	Stacking-inspired pipeline optimizer using evolutionary algorithms.	[P18]
PMF-based Methods	Uses probabilistic matrix factorization to recommend pipeline configurations.	[P18]

A.5 Evaluation Methods in AutoML

Table 5 summarizes common evaluation methods employed across AutoML systems to assess model performance.

Table 5: Evaluation Methods in AutoML

Evaluation Method	Description	Tools/Examples
Low-Fidelity Evaluation	Approximates full evaluation using data subsets or lower-resolution datasets.	FABOLAS, Transfer Series Expansion [P10]
Weight Sharing	Reuses weights across architectures in NAS to reduce cost. Achieves massive speedups.	ENAS, Single-Path NAS, AutoHAS [P10,P15]
Surrogate Models	Predicts model performance using learned models like GPs, CNNs, or RNNs.	SemiNAS [P10,P20]
Early Stopping	Stops unpromising models early using learning curves or validation scores.	DARTS+ [P21,P15]
Multi-Fidelity / Bandit Methods	Dynamically allocates budgets across trials based on performance.	SuccessiveHalving, Hyperband, FABOLAS [P21,P20]
Scalability	Employs parallel/distributed evaluation. Surrogate models can run in parallel.	SMBO variants, Cloud-based AutoML [P21]
Ensemble Learning	Combines multiple models for improved generalization.	Stacked Ensembles [P21]
Interpretability in Evaluation	Assesses model transparency along with accuracy.	LIME, PDP, Vertex AI [P7,P6]
Evaluation in NAS	Reduces NAS cost using one-shot, zero-shot, or resource-aware evaluation.	One-shot NAS, Zero-shot NAS, DARTS, resource-aware NAS [P15]
Metrics and Deployment	Uses standard classification/regression metrics. Includes post-deployment monitoring.	AUC-ROC, MAE, R^2 , Vertex AI [P6]

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